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1 **Underground pumped storage hydropower plants using open pit mines: how do**
2 **groundwater exchanges influence the efficiency?**

3

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18

19 **Abstract**

20 Underground Pumped Storage Hydropower (UPSH) is a potential alternative to
21 manage electricity production in flat regions. UPSH plants will interact with the
22 surrounding porous medium through exchanges of groundwater. These exchanges may
23 impact the surrounding aquifers, but they may also influence the efficiency of the pumps
24 and turbines because affecting the head difference between the reservoirs. Despite the
25 relevance for an accurate efficiency assessment, the influence of the groundwater
26 exchanges has not been previously addressed.

27 A numerical study of a synthetic case is presented to highlight the importance of
28 considering the groundwater exchanges with the surrounding porous medium. The
29 general methodology is designed in order to be further applied in the decision making of
30 future UPSH plants introducing each case specific complexity. The underground
31 reservoir of a hypothetical UPSH plant, which consists in an open pit mine, is
32 considered and modelled together with the surrounding porous medium. Several
33 scenarios with different characteristics are simulated and their results are compared in
34 terms of (1) head difference between the upper and lower reservoirs, and (2) efficiency
35 by considering the theoretical performance curves of a pump and a turbine. The results
36 show that the efficiency is improved when the groundwater exchanges increase. Thus,
37 the highest efficiencies will be reached when (1) the underground reservoir is located in
38 a transmissive porous medium, and (2) the walls of the open pit mine do not constrain
39 the groundwater exchanges (they are not waterproofed). However, a compromise must
40 be found because the characteristics that increase the efficiency also increase the
41 environmental impacts. Meaningful and reliable results are computed in relation to the
42 characteristics of the intermittent and expected stops of UPSH plants. The frequency of
43 pumping and injection must be considered to properly configure the pumps and turbines

44 of future UPSH plants. If not, pumps and turbines could operate far from their best
45 efficiency conditions.

46

47 **Keywords:** Pumped Storage, Hydropower, Energy Storage, Open pit, Efficiency,
48 Groundwater.

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Over 81% of the total energy consumed in the world, of which $\approx 58\%$ is
51 represented by electricity generation in the countries members of the Organisation for
52 Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), is obtained from fossil fuels (IEA,
53 2016). This dependence is not sustainable because fossil fuels are limited and impact
54 the environment (e.g., the greenhouse effect). It is therefore necessary to develop
55 renewable sources of energy to replace the electricity obtained from fossil fuels in the
56 near future.

57 The most important concern with respect to some forms of renewable energy,
58 such as solar and wind energies, is their intermittence and the fact that their production
59 over time cannot be matched to variations in demand (Hu et al., 2016, Mileva et al.,
60 2016, Okazaki et al., 2016, Athari and Ardehali, 2016, Giordano et al., 2016). Therefore,
61 energy storage systems have become the key to improve the efficiency of renewable
62 energy and increase its utilization (Gebretsadik et al., 2016). Energy storage systems
63 allow the production of electricity to be managed according to the demand (Mason,
64 2015, Delfanti et al., 2015). These systems allow the excess energy to be stored during
65 low demand periods and producing electricity when the demand increases.

66 Pumped Storage Hydropower (PSH) is one of the most commonly used storage
67 systems (Zhang et al., 2015) because it allows large amounts of electricity to be stored
68 and produced (Steffen, 2012). PSH plants, which consist of two reservoirs located at
69 different heights, allow a large percentage ($\approx 70\%$) of the excess electricity generated
70 during the low demand periods to be reused (Chen et al., 2009). However, PSH
71 technology is constrained by topography and land availability because it requires a
72 minimum elevation difference between the two reservoirs as well as large volumes
73 (Mueller et al., 2015). In addition, PSH plants are controversial due to their impacts on

74 landscape, land use, environment (vegetation and wildlife) and society (relocations)
75 (Wong, 1996, Kucukali, 2014).

76 Conversely, Underground Pumped Storage Hydropower (UPSH) (Uddin, 2003)
77 is an alternative to store and manage large amounts of electricity that is not limited by
78 topography. Consequently, more sites are available (Meyer, 2013). UPSH plants consist
79 of two reservoirs; the upper reservoir is located at the surface or at shallow depth, while
80 the lower reservoir is underground. Although the underground reservoir can be drilled
81 (Madlener and Specht, 2013), the cheapest (and possibly most efficient) alternative
82 consists of using abandoned works, such as deep or open pit mines (Alvarado et al.,
83 2015, Bodeux et al., 2016). Impacts on land use, vegetation and wildlife produced by
84 UPSH are lower than those of PSH because (at least) one of the reservoirs is
85 underground. However, it is needed to consider the effects of UPSH plants on
86 surrounding porous media to quantify the total environmental impact. Social impacts of
87 UPSH plants are also lower because 1) less relocations are required (the lower
88 reservoir is underground), and 2) the reuse of abandoned mines contributes adding
89 value to local communities after the cessation of mining activities. In addition,
90 sedimentation problems should be also lower in UPSH plants because used
91 groundwater is filtered by the porous medium. Sedimentation problems could probably
92 appear by eroded materials from the open pit walls.

93 Despite of the benefits, there are no bibliographic evidence of UPSH plants
94 constructed. However, some studies and projects have been mentioned and developed
95 until now. During 1980's a project to install an UPSH plant was launched in the
96 Netherlands (Braat et al., 1985), but the plant was not finally constructed for different
97 reasons such as the inadequate characteristics of the soil (Spriet, 2014). Wong (1996)
98 assessed the possibility of construct UPSH plants in Singapore using abandoned rock
99 quarries as upper reservoirs. In this case, Wong (1996) proposed to drill tunnels or

100 shafts to be used as underground reservoirs. Severson (2011) evaluated the potential of
101 ten sites to establish an underground taconite mine in Minnesota (USA) whose cavity
102 would be after used as lower reservoir for an UPSH plant. Some preliminary studies
103 have been also carried out in Germany to assess the possibilities for construct UPSH
104 plants on abandoned mines in the Harz and Ruhr regions (Niemann, 2011, Beck, 2011,
105 Luick et al., 2012). Finally, Spriet (2013) explored the possibility for constructing an
106 UPSH plant in Martelange (Belgium).

107 Underground works are rarely isolated, and groundwater exchanges between
108 UPSH plants and the surrounding porous medium will occur if they are used as
109 underground reservoirs. In addition to the impacts on groundwater levels (Pujades et
110 al., 2016, Bodeux et al., 2016), groundwater exchanges may affect the efficiency of
111 UPSH plants. The efficiency of the pumps and turbines depends on the head difference
112 between the upper and the lower reservoirs. This head difference, which varies over
113 time and can be easily predicted in PSH plants (i.e. with waterproof reservoirs), may be
114 influenced by the groundwater exchanges in UPSH plants. Therefore, it is crucial to
115 determine the influence of these exchanges on the head difference between the
116 reservoirs and consequently on UPSH efficiency. This would allow the efficiency of
117 future UPSH plants to be improved by selecting pumps and turbines adapted to the
118 effective groundwater exchanges with the surrounding porous medium. However, no
119 studies in the literature have focused on this issue.

120 In this study, a synthetic case of an UPSH plant that utilizes an open pit mine as
121 underground reservoir is considered, and the relationship between the groundwater
122 exchanges and the efficiency of the pumps and turbines is studied numerically. The
123 influence of groundwater exchanges on the efficiency and how this varies depending on
124 the system properties (porous medium parameters, open pit mine characteristics and
125 pumping/injection features) are investigated. The main objective is to highlight the

126 paramount importance of considering groundwater exchanges during the design stage
127 of future UPSH plants.

128

129 **2. Materials and methods**

130 2.1. Problem statement

131 The problem is formulated as shown in Figure 1. A hypothetical UPSH plant
132 whose underground reservoir is an open pit mine is considered. Of course, actual
133 properties of open pit mines are more complex, but the goal of the paper is, at this
134 stage, to assess the general relevance of groundwater exchanges in terms of efficiency.
135 Still, some characteristics of the adopted geometry (e.g. the mine flooded depth) are
136 similar to some actual geometries of open pit lakes in Western Europe (Deminal et al.,
137 2005). The geometry of the open pit mine is conceptually simplified as a square cuboid
138 (top and bottom faces are squares) with a depth of 100 m to facilitate the numerical
139 study while obtaining representative results. This geometrical simplification may affect
140 the volume of groundwater exchanges but not the assessment of their influence on the
141 efficiency of UPSH plants. The initial hydraulic head under natural conditions (without
142 pumping or injection) is located at a depth of 50 m. As a result, half of the open pit is
143 saturated.

144 The whole thickness (100 m) of the surrounding porous medium is assumed
145 homogeneous and isotropic. The water table is located at a depth of 50 m. Therefore,
146 under natural conditions, it is a 50-m-thick unconfined porous medium. The numerical
147 model has a flat geometry for representing a typical horizontal layered geology. The
148 external boundaries are chosen located at 2500 m from the reservoir to minimize their
149 impact on the simulated evolution of the hydraulic head inside the open pit mine. Their
150 impacts are lower and are later observed as further the boundaries are located.

151 Additional simulations were performed reducing the length of the model to ensure that
152 the flat shape of the modelled domain does not affect the results.

153 The evolution of the hydraulic head in the underground reservoir is computed to
154 assess the differences between the simulations. Given that the objective is to assess
155 the impact of the groundwater exchanges on the efficiency, a very large and shallow
156 upper reservoir is assumed to eliminate its influence on the results (i.e., the increments
157 of the head difference in the upper reservoir produced by its repeated filling and
158 emptying are neglected). Consequently, the computed head difference is only based on
159 the evolution of the hydraulic head in the underground reservoir.

160 Actual frequency of pumping and injection phases of future UPSH plant cannot
161 be forecasted because it depends on a lot of factors (day, season, meteorological
162 conditions if wind or solar energies are the main energy resources, electrical smart grid
163 optimization scenarios...). Thus, to obtain representative results, the frequency
164 adopted in most of the simulations was deduced from a 1 year actual electricity price
165 curve (Pujades et al., 2016) where it is possible to observe that there are two peaks of
166 electricity price the most of the days. Consequently, the simulated pumping and
167 injection phases have durations of 0.25 day. Five theoretical hypotheses are considered
168 for the frequency/intermittence of the pumping and injection. Figure 2 shows the
169 evolutions of the 5 pumping and injection rates over the first five simulated days. For
170 one hypothesis, the frequency, duration and rates of pumping and injection are kept
171 constant for the entire simulation time (500 days). The first hypothesis consists of
172 continuous pumping and injection (stops are not considered). Periods of inactivity are
173 considered in Hypotheses 2 to 5. Hypothesis 2 considers a 0.5 day period of inactivity
174 after each injection, Hypothesis 3 considers 0.5 days of inactivity after each pumping
175 phase, Hypothesis 4 considers 1 day of inactivity after every two injection phases, and
176 Hypothesis 5 considers 1 day of inactivity after every two pumping phases. The

177 pumping and injection rates are 2 m³/s, and the mean hydraulic power is thus 1 MW. In
178 contrast to reality, the considered pumping/injection hypotheses are not complex.
179 Nevertheless, these scenarios allow the main trends of the system to be determined.

180

181 2.2. Numerical model

182 The finite element numerical code SUFT3D (Brouyère et al., 2009 and
183 Wildemeersch et al., 2010) is used to model the underground reservoir and its
184 interactions with the porous medium. This code uses the Control Volume Finite
185 Element (CVFE) method to solve the groundwater flow equation based on the mixed
186 formulation of Richard's equation proposed by Celia et al. (1990):

$$187 \quad \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \underline{\nabla} \cdot \underline{K}(\theta) \cdot \underline{\nabla} h + \underline{\nabla} \cdot \underline{K}(\theta) \cdot \underline{\nabla} z + q \quad (1)$$

188 where θ is the water content [-], t is the time [T], \underline{K} is the hydraulic conductivity
189 tensor [LT⁻¹], h is the pressure head [L], z is the elevation [L], and q is a source/sink
190 term [T⁻¹]. Figure 1b shows an image of the numerical model. The mesh is made up
191 of prismatic 3D elements and is divided vertically into 16 layers, whose respective
192 thicknesses are reduced in the zone around the initial water table. The layers near
193 the water table are 1 m thick, while the top and bottom layers are 10 m thick. The
194 horizontal size of the elements decreases towards the underground reservoir (from
195 500 m near the boundaries to 10 m in the centre of the domain). The validity of the
196 mesh has been tested by ensuring that results are not sensitive to mesh refinements.

197 The underground reservoir is modelled as a linear reservoir and is discretized
198 as a single mixing cell. The velocity inside the mixing cell is neglected. An internal
199 dynamic Fourier boundary condition (BC), which is a head-dependent BC, between
200 the underground reservoir and the surrounding porous medium (Wildemeersch et al.,

201 2010) is used to simulate the groundwater exchanges. The internal Fourier BC is
 202 defined as follows:

$$203 \quad Q_i = \alpha' A (h_{aq} - h_{ur}) \quad (2)$$

204 where Q_i is the exchanged flow [L^3T^{-1}], h_{aq} is the piezometric head in the porous
 205 medium [L], h_{ur} is the hydraulic head in the underground reservoir [L], A is the
 206 exchange surface [L^2], and α' is the exchange coefficient [T^{-1}], with $\alpha' = (K'/b')$,
 207 where K' and b' are the hydraulic conductivity [LT^{-1}] and the width [L] of the lining,
 208 respectively. Different lining conditions are considered by varying the value of α' ;
 209 non-lined walls are simulated with high values of α' . Given that the maximum value
 210 of K' cannot be greater than the hydraulic conductivity of the porous medium (K),
 211 high values of α' allow simulating a very thin lining as conductive as the porous
 212 medium. It is possible to deduce from Eq. 2 that groundwater exchanges vary linearly
 213 as a function of the difference in water level between the reservoir and the
 214 surrounding porous medium (Orban and Brouyère, 2006).

215 The retention curve and the relative hydraulic conductivity are defined as
 216 follows (Yeh, 1987):

$$217 \quad \theta = \theta_r + \frac{(\theta_s - \theta_r)}{h_b - h_a} (h - h_a) \quad (3)$$

$$218 \quad K_r(\theta) = \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} \quad (4),$$

219 where θ_s is the saturated water content [-], θ_r is the residual water content [-], K_r is
 220 the relative hydraulic conductivity [LT^{-1}], h_b is the pressure head at which the water
 221 content is the same as the residual water content [L], and h_a is the pressure head at
 222 which the water content is less than the saturated water content [L]. The parameters

223 h_a and h_b are taken as 0 and -5 m, respectively, and are held constant in all of the
224 scenarios. The law that is used to define the transition between the partially saturated
225 and saturated zones is chosen for its linearity. It does not affect the results of this
226 study, which focuses on the saturated zone, and eliminates convergence errors that
227 can appear using other laws.

228 Dirichlet BCs are adopted at the external boundaries of the numerical model.
229 These BCs consists of prescribing the piezometric head at a depth of 50 m (the same
230 as the initial piezometric head). It is assumed that the volume of water provided by a
231 hypothetical recharge or from a lower stratum is negligible. Consequently, no-flow BCs
232 are adopted at the top and bottom boundaries.

233 A set of numerical simulations are performed, and their results are compared to
234 assess the influence of the system variables on the efficiency. The assessed (and
235 modified) variables are K , θ_s , the storage capacity of the open pit mine, α' and the
236 frequency of the pumping and injection phases. The latter is achieved by considering
237 the 5 hypotheses shown in Figure 2.

238

239 2.3. Basic concepts

240 *2.3.1. Evolution of the head difference between the upper and underground* 241 *reservoirs*

242 Figure 3 shows the evolution of the head difference between the upper and the
243 lower reservoirs for the entire time period (Figure 3a) and during the first 10 simulated
244 days (Figure 3b). The head difference evolution is computed with the numerical model
245 by considering a reference scenario with the following characteristics: $K=1$ m/d, $\theta_s=0.1$,
246 $\alpha'=1000$ d⁻¹ (i.e., no lining is simulated), and the pumping and injection phases are
247 continuous (Hypothesis 1).

248 The head difference oscillates as a result of the water pumping and injection.
249 The mid-range head difference, which is computed from the maximum and minimum
250 head difference during each pumping and injection cycle, increases in the first cycle as
251 a result of the first pumping phase and decreases progressively over time. After a
252 period of time that depends on the characteristics of the problem, the mid-range head
253 difference becomes constant, and a dynamic steady state is reached. The attained mid-
254 range head difference depends on the pumping/injection hypothesis. In the simulated
255 scenario, the mid-range head difference when the dynamic steady state is reached is
256 the same as the initial head difference (50 m) because the adopted pumping/injection
257 hypothesis is “symmetrical”. The progressive decrease of the mid-range head difference
258 is caused by the groundwater exchanges between the underground reservoir and the
259 surrounding porous medium, which increases the hydraulic head in the reservoir.
260 Groundwater flows in when the hydraulic head in the reservoir is lower than the
261 piezometric head in the surrounding porous medium and flows out in the opposite
262 situation. During the early cycles, most of the groundwater exchanges are inflows
263 because the hydraulic head is lower than the piezometric head during longer time
264 periods. The time interval of each cycle during which the hydraulic head is lower
265 decreases progressively with increasing cycles, and after several cycles, this time
266 interval lasts half of the cycle. At that moment, the hydraulic head is higher than the
267 piezometric head during the other half of the cycle. When this occurs, the dynamic
268 steady state has been reached, and the groundwater inflows and outflows during each
269 cycle are the same. As a result of this behaviour, the rate of decrease of the mid-range
270 head difference is higher at the beginning, and it decreases over time to 0.

271 The magnitude of the oscillations, the variation of the mid-range head difference
272 and the time to reach the dynamic steady state depend on the system properties and
273 are essential to study the impact of the groundwater exchanges on the UPSH efficiency.

274

275 *2.3.2. Efficiency of pumps and turbines*

276 For a constant rotation speed, the efficiency of pumps and turbines is defined
277 by a pair of performance curves similar to those shown in Figure 4 (Chapallaz et al.,
278 1992). These curves relate the head difference and the efficiency with the
279 pumping/injection rate. The best efficiency point (BEP), which is defined by the
280 performance curves, is the point at which the efficiency is the maximum for a given
281 head difference and pumping/injection rate. The head difference between the
282 reservoirs, and therefore the efficiency, varies during the pumping and injection phases.
283 As a result of this variation, pumps and turbines operate in a range of efficiencies that is
284 called the “operation range”. If the head difference defined by the BEP of the machine is
285 consistent with the mid-range head difference, the BEP is centred with respect to the
286 operation range. The efficiency increases as the operation range decreases. Therefore,
287 higher efficiencies are reached when the change in the head differences between the
288 reservoirs produced by the pumping and injection is smaller. It is also important to
289 consider the variation of the mid-range head difference over time because it affects the
290 efficiency. The efficiency only reaches its maximum value when the head difference
291 defined by the BEP is consistent with the mid-range head difference. Therefore, if
292 pumps and turbines are selected based on the mid-range head difference when the
293 dynamic steady state is reached, the efficiency is lower at early times and increases
294 progressively until achieving a maximum when the dynamic steady state is reached.

295 Groundwater exchanges between the open pit mine and the surrounding porous
296 medium modify the hydraulic head inside the underground reservoir. Therefore, they
297 may reduce or increase the operation ranges of the pumps and turbines and induce
298 variations of the mid-range head difference over time. The efficiency will be higher when
299 the magnitude of the oscillations and the variations of the mid-range head difference

300 over time are lower. The time to reach the dynamic steady state should also be
301 considered to assess the efficiency of UPSH plants. In the case of long stops (expected
302 or not), during which the head difference between the reservoirs returns to its initial
303 value, less time is required by the pumps and turbines to oscillate around the chosen
304 BEP if the time to reach the dynamic steady state is shorter.

305 Actual performance curves of a pump and a turbine are used to support the
306 numerical results of this study. The BEP defined by these performance curves is
307 reached when the head difference is 50 m, which is consistent with the mid-range head
308 difference when the dynamic steady state is reached assuming continuous pumping
309 and injection cycles (Hypothesis 1) with a nominal pumping/injection rate of $2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The
310 code used to model the groundwater flow does not allow the non-linear function that is
311 defined by the performance curves and relates the pumping and injection rates to the
312 head difference to be introduced. Therefore, performance curves of variable speed
313 machines and a constant flow rate are used to assess the variations on the efficiency
314 induced by groundwater exchanges. These curves, which are obtained from the
315 performance curves of constant speed machines by applying the affinity laws of pumps
316 and turbines (Chapallaz et al., 1992), relate the speed of rotation and the efficiency with
317 the head difference between the upper and lower reservoirs for a constant flow rate.
318 Figure 5 shows the performance curves for variable speed machines used in this study.
319 Note that head losses are not considered. The equations that define these curves were
320 derived by Microsoft Excel 2013. They served to compute analytically the efficiency by
321 using the head difference obtained from the numerical model.

322

323 **3. Results and discussions**

324 3.1. Evolution of the average efficiency

325 Figure 6 shows the average efficiency evolution for 5 scenarios (Sce1 to Sce5).
326 One variable is modified in each scenario with respect to scenario 1 (Sce1) to determine
327 its individual effect on the evolution of the average efficiency. The characteristics of
328 Sce1 are as follows: $K=1 \text{ m}^2/\text{d}$, $\theta_s=0.1$, $\alpha'=1000 \text{ d}^{-1}$, the saturated volume of the mine
329 (V_{UR}) is $500,000 \text{ m}^3$, and Hypothesis 1 is considered for the pumping and injection
330 phases. The value of K is 10 m/d in Sce2, θ_s is 0.2 in Sce3, α' is 0.01 d^{-1} in Sce4, and
331 V_{UR} is $250,000 \text{ m}^3$ in Sce5.

332 Average efficiency shown in Figure 6 is computed by the following steps: 1) a
333 value of efficiency is calculated for each of the simulated time steps, which make up the
334 pumping and injection phases, by using the head difference computed numerically and
335 the performance curves displayed in figure 5; 2) the calculated efficiencies are averaged
336 over each pumping and injection phase to obtain their average efficiency; and 3) the
337 average efficiency over each pumping and injection phase is plotted versus time. Figure
338 6 only shows the average value of the efficiency. Efficiency oscillations produced by
339 pumping and injection, and therefore, the maximum and minimum efficiencies reached
340 during each phase are not considered in this figure.

341 The average efficiency increases over time until it reaches a maximum and
342 constant value. The maximum efficiency is reached when the dynamic steady state is
343 achieved and the mid-range head difference between the reservoirs is the same as the
344 head difference defined by the BEP of the pump and the turbine. The lowest efficiencies
345 are observed for Sce5 because the storage capacity of the underground reservoir is
346 decreased in this scenario. Consequently, the magnitude of the oscillations, and
347 therefore the operation ranges of the pump and the turbine, are higher.

348 The average efficiencies of scenarios Sce1 to Sce4 differ in the early times
349 because the time required by the pump and the turbine to operate around their BEPs
350 are different; it is shorter for Sce2 and longer for Sce4. This behaviour highlights the

351 importance of the time required to reach the dynamic steady state to the efficiency in
352 the case of long periods of inactivity. Pumps and turbines will need less time to operate
353 around their BEPs if the dynamic steady state is reached more quickly. Note that if long
354 periods of inactivity are frequent and the dynamic steady state is never reached, the
355 efficiency could be improved by selecting pumps and turbines whose BEP is adapted to
356 the head differences during the early cycles (higher than during the dynamic steady
357 state).

358 Finally, the maximum efficiencies that are reached during the injection phases
359 are not the same for scenarios Sce1 to Sce4. Higher efficiencies are reached for Sce2
360 because the magnitude of the oscillations, and therefore the operation ranges of the
361 turbine, are smaller. Differences in the average efficiency of the pump are not observed
362 because its performance curves are softer than those of the turbine. As a result, the
363 efficiency of the pump varies less depending on the head difference.

364

365 3.2. Hydraulic conductivity of the porous medium (K)

366 The numerical results of 5 scenarios (Sce 6 to Sce10) with different values of K
367 are summarized in Figure 7. The common characteristics of these scenarios are as
368 follows: $\theta_s=0.1$, $\alpha'=1000 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $V_{UR}=500,000 \text{ m}^3$, and Hypothesis 1 is considered for the
369 pumping and injection phases. The values of K are 0.1 m/d in Sce6, 1 m/d in Sce7, 10
370 m/d in Sce8, 100 m/d in Sce9 and 1000 m/d in Sce10.

371 Figure 7a shows the head variations in the reservoir. The mid-range head
372 difference, the magnitude of the oscillations and the time required to reach the dynamic
373 steady state decrease with higher values of K . As a result, the pumps and turbines
374 operate closer to the BEP in transmissive porous media (i.e. their efficiency is higher).
375 The magnitude of the oscillations and the variation of the mid-range head difference are
376 similar for values of K lower than 10 m/d. In these cases, the efficiency depends on the

377 time required to reach the dynamic steady state. Figure 7b shows the operation ranges
378 for Sce6 to Sce10. These operation ranges are computed when the dynamic steady
379 state is reached. The operation ranges of the pumps and turbines are smaller for higher
380 values of K . Consequently, higher values of K improve the efficiency of the pumps and
381 turbines.. The operation ranges are similar for Sce6 to Sce8 because the groundwater
382 exchanges and head variations are similar for values of K lower than 10 m/d. It is
383 possible to calculate by using the performance curves (Figure 5) the minimum efficiency
384 reached during pumping and injection phases once the dynamic steady state is
385 achieved. 87.2 % (pumping) and 91.2 % (injection) are the minimum efficiencies for
386 Sce6, while 87.8 % (pumping) and 91.7 % (injection) are the minimum efficiencies for
387 Sce10. These results corroborate that the efficiency of pumps and turbines is improved
388 with higher K . These values are only illustrative because they will vary depending on the
389 characteristics of pumps and turbines.

390

391 3.3. Storage coefficient of the surrounding porous medium

392 The influence of the storage coefficient of the surrounding porous medium (S) is
393 assessed by varying θ_s in four scenarios (Sce11 to Sce14). Their common
394 characteristics are as follows: $K=1$ m/d, $\alpha'=1000$ d⁻¹, $V_{UR}=500,000$ m³, and Hypothesis
395 1 is considered for the pumping and injection phases. The values of θ_s are 0.05 in
396 Sce11, 0.1 in Sce12, 0.2 in Sce13 and 0.3 in Sce14.

397 Figure 8a summarizes the head variations. The groundwater exchanges increase
398 with higher values of θ_s ; however, this increase is relatively small, and the differences
399 between the magnitudes of the oscillations and the variation of the mid-range head
400 difference are negligible. Similar results are observed in Figure 8b, which shows the
401 operation ranges when the dynamic steady state is reached. The operation ranges are
402 nearly the same for all scenarios (i.e., the symbols that represent each scenario

403 overlap). The time to reach the dynamic steady state is the only characteristic that
404 varies significantly between the scenarios. Thus, S modifies the time required by the
405 pumps and turbines to operate around their BEPs. These results suggest that S is an
406 important variable when long periods of inactivity, during which the head difference
407 between the reservoirs returns to its initial value, may occur. Less time is needed to
408 reach the dynamic steady state and oscillate around the selected BEP when S
409 decreases.

410

411 3.4. Exchange coefficient (α')

412 The influence of α' is evaluated by comparing the numerical results of six
413 scenarios (Sce15 to Sce20). The common features of the scenarios are as follows:
414 $K=10$ m/d, $\theta_s=0.1$, $V_{UR}=500,000$ m³, and Hypothesis 1 is considered for the pumping
415 and injection phases. The values of α' are 0.01 d⁻¹ in Sce 15, 0.1 d⁻¹ in Sce16, 1 d⁻¹ for
416 Sce17, 10 d⁻¹ in Sce18, 100 d⁻¹ in Sce19 and 1000 d⁻¹ in Sce20.

417 The head variations (Figure 9a) and the operation ranges of the pumps and
418 turbines (Figure 9b) are similar in all of the scenarios. The most noticeable difference is
419 in the time required to reach the dynamic steady state, which increases with lower
420 values of α' (but not significantly). Although α' controls the groundwater exchanges, if
421 the porous medium cannot provide enough water, its influence is not noticed. As shown
422 in Figure 7, the head differences are similar in scenarios Sce1, Sce2 and Sce3, which
423 suggests that the groundwater exchanges are similar for values of K lower than 10 m/d.
424 Therefore, head variations are similar in Sce15 to Sce20 because the groundwater
425 exchanges are constrained by the porous medium. Thus, influence of α' is limited and
426 groundwater exchanges do not vary significantly..

427 K is increased to 100 m/d in scenarios 21 to 26 to ascertain the influence of α' .

428 The other common characteristics of the scenarios are: $\theta_s=0.1$, $V_{UR}=500,000$ m³, and

429 Hypothesis 1 is considered for the pumping and injection phases. The values of α' are
430 0.01 d^{-1} in Sce21, 0.1 d^{-1} in Sce22, 1 d^{-1} in Sce23, 10 d^{-1} in Sce24, 100 d^{-1} in Sce25 and
431 1000 d^{-1} in Sce26.

432 Figures 10a and 10b show the head variations and the operation ranges,
433 respectively. The influence of α' is greater because the groundwater exchanges are
434 constrained less by the porous medium properties. The magnitude of the oscillations,
435 the variation of the mid-range head difference and the time to reach the dynamic steady
436 state decrease with higher values of α' because the groundwater exchanges increase.
437 Consequently, the operation ranges are smaller for higher values of α' . The head
438 variations (magnitude of the oscillations and variation of the mid-range head difference)
439 and operation ranges are similar for values of α' higher than 100 d^{-1} because the
440 simulated interface between the porous medium and the underground reservoir is more
441 conductive than the porous medium. In these situations, the groundwater exchanges
442 are only constrained by the porous medium parameters, which are the same in all of the
443 scenarios. Although the head variations and operation ranges are also similar for values
444 of α' lower than 1 d^{-1} , the groundwater exchanges vary between Sce21, Sce22 and
445 Sce23 that can be deduced from the time required to reach the dynamic steady state,
446 which increases with lower values of α' .

447 These results suggest that applying waterproof treatments to the walls could be
448 counter-productive in terms of efficiency because higher efficiencies occur when the
449 walls do not constrain the groundwater exchanges. An exception with respect to the
450 time required to reach the dynamic steady state occurs if the walls are completely
451 waterproof. In this case, the mid-range head difference remains constant and the BEP
452 is reached immediately. However, it is difficult to completely isolate underground
453 cavities because construction defects are relatively common (Bruce et al., 1989,

454 Vilarrasa et al., 2011, Pujades et al., 2012, Pujades et al., 2016). The operation ranges
455 of pumps and turbines would be higher with completely waterproof walls.

456

457 3.5. Storage capacity of the underground reservoir (V_{UR})

458 The results from four scenarios (Sce27 to Sce29) are compared to determine the
459 importance of the storage capacity of the underground reservoir to the efficiency. The
460 common features of the scenarios are as follows: $K=1$ m/d, $\theta_s=0.1$, $\alpha'=1000$ d⁻¹, and
461 Hypothesis 1 is considered for the pumping and injection phases. The values of V_{UR} are
462 125,000 m³ in Sce26, 250,000 m³ in Sce27, 500,000 m³ in Sce28 and 1,000,000 m³ in
463 Sce29. Note that only the storage capacity of the underground reservoir is modified to
464 assess its influence separately. The geometry (i.e. size) is not varied to eliminate effects
465 produced on the groundwater exchanges by an increment of the exchange surface
466 between the underground reservoir and the surrounding porous medium.

467 Figure 11a shows the head variations, while Figure 11b shows the operation
468 ranges of the pumps and turbines. The variations of the mid-range head difference and
469 the magnitude of the oscillations decrease significantly when larger storage capacities
470 are considered. Conversely, the time to reach the dynamic steady state increases.
471 Similarly, the size of the operation ranges decreases with larger storage capacities. The
472 percentages of pumped or injected water that flows from or to the porous medium (i.e.,
473 groundwater exchanges) decrease with larger storage capacities. Thus, these results
474 do not match with the previous ones because the efficiency increases with lower
475 groundwater exchanges, which can be interpreted from the increase in the time to reach
476 the dynamic steady state. In these scenarios, the decrease in efficiency associated to
477 the reduction of the groundwater exchanges is compensated by the contraction of the
478 operation ranges that occur when the storage capacity is increased keeping constants
479 the pumping and injection rates.

480

481 3.6. Frequency of the pumping and injection intervals

482 The previous simulations were performed considering the continuous activity of
483 the plant (Hypothesis 1). However, stops will probably be common and required in
484 UPSH plants to manage the electricity production. Five scenarios (Sce31 to Sce35) that
485 differ in the frequency and the duration of the stops are compared. The common
486 characteristics of the scenarios are as follows: $K=1$ m/d, $\theta_s=0.1$, $\alpha'=1000$ d⁻¹,
487 $V_{UR}=500,000$ m³, and Q_P and Q_I are 2 m³/s. Sce31 is based on Hypothesis 1
488 (continuous pumping and injection), Sce32 is based on Hypothesis 2 (0.5 days of
489 inactivity after each injection phase), Sce33 is based on Hypothesis 3 (0.5 days of
490 inactivity after each pumping phase), Sce34 is based on Hypothesis 4 (1 day of
491 inactivity after every two injections phases) and Sce35 is based on Hypothesis 5 (1 day
492 of inactivity after every two pumping phases).

493 Figure 12 summarizes the numerical results of Scenarios 31 to 35. The
494 magnitude of the oscillations does not depend on the frequency and the duration of the
495 period of inactivity. For this reason, the amplitudes of the operation ranges of the pumps
496 and turbines are similar in all of the scenarios (Figure 11b). The main differences in the
497 head variations are the time required to reach the dynamic steady state and the
498 variation of the mid-range head difference with time. On the one hand, more time is
499 needed to reach the dynamic steady state when stops occur after the injection phases.
500 This time decreases if the periods of inactivity are shorter. Thus, if the pumps and
501 turbines are properly selected considering the final mid-range head difference, it would
502 be advisable to carry out the periods of inactivity after pumping intervals. On the other
503 hand, the variations of the mid-range head difference over time are greater when the
504 stops occur after phases of pumping. Changes in the variation of the mid-range head
505 difference are produced because the final value of the mid-range head difference with

506 respect to the initial head difference between the reservoirs varies depending on the
507 characteristics of the inactivity periods. While the final value of the mid-range head
508 difference is the same as the initial head difference (before the UPSH plant starts
509 operating) in Hypothesis 1, it is greater in Hypotheses 2 and 4 and smaller in
510 Hypotheses 3 and 5. This fact must be carefully considered in the selection of pumps
511 and turbines for future UPSH plants. If not, the pumps and turbines could operate far
512 from their BEP. This behaviour and its consequences are shown more clearly in Figure
513 12b. The relative position of the BEP (centred or not centred with respect to the
514 operation range) varies depending on the hypothesis. The BEP is not located in the
515 middle of the operation ranges in Sce31 to 34. The variation in the mid-range head
516 difference from the initial conditions until the dynamic steady state is reached is smaller
517 when the periods of inactivity occur after the injections and greater when the stops
518 occur after pumping.

519 The efficiency of future UPSH plants can be improved by considering the
520 characteristics of the expected and regular stops. If the value of the final mid-range
521 head difference is adequately predicted and is considered in the selection of the pumps
522 and turbines, the BEP will be centred with respect to the operation range. Note that the
523 considered pumping/injection hypotheses are “simple” and predictable. However, they
524 allow the main behaviours of the system to be ascertained. In real situations, the
525 pumping/injection frequencies will be more heterogeneous.

526

527 3.7. Scale effects

528 The mean hydraulic power of the considered UPSH plant is 1 MW, which is not
529 so much in comparison with actual PSH plants. Consequently, the scale effect on the
530 results must be considered to establish if the influence of groundwater exchanges will
531 be the same in larger UPSH plants. Higher hydraulic power will be reached by

532 increasing the injection rate, which means (1) underground reservoirs with higher
533 storage capacity or, (2) higher head oscillations. If the increment of the storage capacity
534 induces an increment of the exchange surface, groundwater exchanges will also
535 increase (note that in this study the exchange surface is kept constant to assess only
536 the influence of the storage capacity). If higher head oscillations are produced,
537 groundwater exchanges will also increase because the hydraulic gradient between the
538 porous medium and the reservoir will be higher. Higher hydraulic power could be also
539 reached by planning the plant in a site with deeper underground reservoir and
540 piezometric head. In this case, the influence of the groundwater exchanges on the
541 efficiency will be the same.

542

543 3.8. Environmental impacts

544 The Water Framework Directive (WFD,2000/60/EC) adopted by the European
545 Union in October 2000 establishes that the nations must guarantee the good state of
546 the groundwater bodies, and consequently, pollutants discharges into groundwater are
547 forbidden. In the same manner, this directive states that reinjection of pumped water
548 from mines and quarries is allowed if the discharges do not compromise previous
549 environmental achievements. The most of future UPSH plants will respect the directive
550 because pollutants will theoretically not be discharged since the water released to
551 produce electricity will be that pumped previously. However, the environmental impacts
552 must be rigorously investigated during the design stage of future UPSH plants because
553 some of them could alter the groundwater quality. Piezometric head oscillations could
554 mobilize contaminants contained in the unsaturated zone. In the same manner,
555 hydrochemical modifications could be induced by the exposure of groundwater at the
556 surface (i.e. oxidizing conditions) and further injection. Anyway, previous studies have
557 demonstrated that environmental impacts would be higher as the groundwater

558 exchanges increase (Pujades et al., 2016, Bodeux et al., 2016). Therefore, given that
559 groundwater exchanges are not disadvantageous in terms of efficiency, an agreement
560 should be achieved between the efficiency and the environmental impacts in future
561 UPSH plants.

562

563 **4. Summary and conclusions**

564

565 Open pit mines, which can be used as underground reservoirs of UPSH plants,
566 are rarely isolated. Consequently, water will flow in and out affecting the efficiency of the
567 plant, which should be considered in its design. The main conclusions of this study are:

- 568 • Groundwater exchanges mitigate the head difference variations, which reduces
569 the operation ranges of pumps and turbines. As a result, pumps/turbines
570 operate at higher efficiency in UPSH plants than in classical PSH plants.
- 571 • Groundwater exchanges influence the evolution of the mid-range head
572 difference over time, which must be considered in the selection of the pumps
573 and turbines; otherwise, they could operate far from their BEPs.
- 574 • The time required to reach the dynamic steady state depends on the
575 groundwater exchanges. This issue is important when long periods of inactivity,
576 during which the head difference between the reservoirs returns to its initial
577 value, occur because the pumps and turbines operate before around their BEPs
578 if the dynamic steady state is reached more quickly.
- 579 • The frequency and duration of pumping, injection and periods of inactivity
580 control the final mid-range head difference between the reservoirs, which must
581 be considered to optimize the efficiency.
- 582 • The influence of groundwater exchanges on the efficiency decreases as the
583 storage capacity of the underground reservoir increases. However, if a higher

584 storage capacity implies a largest exchange surface, groundwater exchanges
585 will continue to influence the efficiency.

586 • Water exchanges are not disadvantageous in terms of the efficiency; however,
587 the environmental impacts on the surrounding porous medium are higher as the
588 groundwater exchanges increase. Therefore, a compromise will be needed
589 between the efficiency and the environmental impacts in future UPSH plants.

590 The variation of the efficiency that is caused by the groundwater exchanges
591 when the dynamic steady state is reached is not too significant in this study. However,
592 the influence of the groundwater exchanges will increase if the performance curves of
593 the pumps and turbines are sharper.

594

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603

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718

719 **Figure captions**

720 Figure 1. a) Sketch of the cross section of the problem. b) View of the numerical model.

721 The red dashed lines highlight the area where the Dirichlet BCs are prescribed. The
722 saturated zone of the model is located below the water table.

723 Figure 2. Evolutions of the pumping and injection rates (m^3/s) considered in the
724 simulations. Negative values mean that water is extracted (pumped), while positive
725 values mean that water is released into the open pit mine.

726 Figure 3. a) Evolution of the head difference between the upper and underground
727 reservoirs over the entire simulated time. The dotted and dashed lines indicate the initial
728 head difference between the reservoirs and the mid-range head difference during the
729 first pumping/injection cycle, respectively. b) Detail of the evolution of the head
730 difference during the first 10 simulated days.

731 Figure 4. Performance curves of pumps (left) and turbines (right). These curves define
732 the best efficiency point (BEP). Pumps and turbines operate around the BEP (operation
733 range). Modified from Chapallaz et al. (1992).

734 Figure 5. Actual performance curves of the pump (left) and the turbine (right) considered
735 in this study. The BEP is defined for a head difference of 50 m and a pumping/injection
736 rate of $2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

737 Figure 6. Evolution of the average efficiency during the pumping (left) and injection
738 (right) over 500 days for four simulated scenarios with different characteristics.

739 Figure 7. a) Head variations for 5 scenarios with different values of K of the porous
740 medium. A different background is used to show the time required to reach the dynamic
741 steady state for $K=0.1 \text{ m/d}$ because this time exceeds the simulated time. b) Operation
742 range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

743 Figure 8. a) Head variations for 4 scenarios with different values of S of the porous
744 medium. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the
745 simulated scenarios.

746 Figure 9. a) Head variations for 6 scenarios with different values of α' . The value of K of
747 the porous medium is 10 m/d. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is
748 reached for the simulated scenarios.

749 Figure 10. a) Head variations for 6 scenarios with different values of α' . The value of K
750 of the porous medium is 100 m/d. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is
751 reached for the simulated scenarios.

752 Figure 11. a) Head variations for 4 scenarios with different volumes of the underground
753 reservoir. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the
754 simulated scenarios.

755 Figure 12. a) Head variations for 5 scenarios with different periods of inactivity. The
756 characteristics are varied in each scenario. b) Operation range when the dynamic
757 steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

758

759 **Figures**

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774 Figure 1. Figure 1. a) Sketch of the cross section of the problem. b) View of the
775 numerical model. The red dashed lines highlight the area where the Dirichlet BCs are
776 prescribed. The saturated zone of the model is located below the water table.

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808 Figure 2. Evolutions of the pumping and injection rates (m³/s) considered in the
 809 simulations. Negative values mean that water is extracted (pumped), while positive
 810 values mean that water is released into the open pit mine.

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Figure 3. a) Evolution of the head difference between the upper and underground reservoirs over the entire simulated time. The dotted and dashed lines indicate the initial head difference between the reservoirs and the mid-range head difference during the first pumping/injection cycle, respectively. b) Detail of the evolution of the head difference during the first 10 simulated days.

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Figure 4. Performance curves of pumps (left) and turbines (right). These curves define the best efficiency point (BEP). Pumps and turbines operate around the BEP (operation range). Modified from Chapallaz et al. (1992).

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Figure 5. Actual performance curves of the pump (left) and the turbine (right) considered in this study. The BEP is defined for a head difference of 50 m and a pumping/injection rate of 2 m³/s.

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Figure 6. Evolution of the average efficiency during the pumping (left) and injection (right) over 500 days for four simulated scenarios with different characteristics.

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Figure 7. a) Head variations for 5 scenarios with different values of K of the porous medium. A different background is used to show the time required to reach the dynamic steady state for $K=0.1$ m/d because this time exceeds the simulated time. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

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Figure 8. a) Head variations for 4 scenarios with different values of S of the porous medium. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

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Figure 9. a) Head variations for 6 scenarios with different values of α' . The value of K of the porous medium is 10 m/d. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

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Figure 10. a) Head variations for 6 scenarios with different values of α' . The value of K of the porous medium is 100 m/d. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

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Figure 11. a) Head variations for 4 scenarios with different volumes of the underground reservoir. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.

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Figure 12. a) Head variations for 5 scenarios with different periods of inactivity. The characteristics are varied in each scenario. b) Operation range when the dynamic steady state is reached for the simulated scenarios.